

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHISHEK A R bearing USN 1SU21EC001 has completed his/her minor project on “ *A Zigbee Based Wireless Sensor Network for Sewerage Monitoring* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

Dean, SUIET

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANANYA M GAYATHRI bearing USN 1SU21EC002 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Radar Data Acquisition System* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BHAGYASHREE DEVAREDDI** bearing USN **1SU21EC003** has completed his/her minor project on ***“Home Automation Using DTMF Decoder”*** in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DHINESH KUMAR N B** bearing **USN 1SU21EC004** has completed his/her minor project on ***“Network Monitoring System Communication”*** in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms N CHAYA bearing USN 1SU21EC005 has completed his/her minor project on *“Tanker Robo For Vision Based Surveillance System”* in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms PRAVEEN K J bearing USN 1SU21EC006 has completed his/her minor project on *“An Automatic Mobile Recharger Station”* in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHARANYA U SHETYY bearing USN 1SU21EC007 has completed his/her minor project on “*JPEG2000*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SUMANTH S bearing USN 1SU21EC008 has completed his/her minor project on "*Low Cost Anti-Lock Braking and Traction Control*" in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK KRISHNA S** bearing **USN 1SU21EC009** has completed his/her minor project on “ *Tracking And Positioning System* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADITHYA PRAVEEN** bearing **USN 1SU21EC010** has completed his/her minor project on “*Generation of Electricity from Wind Power*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANANDA KRISHNA NAMBIAR bearing USN 1SU21EC011 has completed his/her minor project on “*Automatic Over Speed Detector*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BHOOMIKA P GATTY KONAJE** bearing USN **1SU21EC012** has completed his/her minor project on “*Local PCO Meter*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FILISHIYA SEQUEIRA** bearing **USN 1SU21EC013** has completed his/her minor project on ***“ Micro Controller based Power Theft Identifier ”*** in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JNANESH KUMAR N P bearing USN 1SU21EC014 has completed his/her minor project on “*Micro Controller based Dissolving Process Controller*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **K SHREYANK** bearing **USN 1SU21EC015** has completed his/her minor project on “*On/Off Control And Data Communication Through Power Line*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEERTESH SANTOSH NAIK** bearing **USN 1SU21EC016** has completed his/her minor project on “**GSM Prepaid EB, Phone Bill System**” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms M CHAITRA RAO bearing USN 1SU21EC017 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Design Of A Color Sensing System For Textile Industries* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MADHURI ACHARYA B** bearing **USN 1SU21EC018** has completed his/her minor project on **“TENS Unit”** in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NAVEEN KUMAR S bearing USN 1SU21EC019 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Packet Analyzer* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIJA V V bearing USN 1SU21EC020 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Ultrasonic Based Distance Measurement System* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PAVAN A bearing USN 1SU21EC021 has completed his/her minor project on “*Remote Vehicle With Unlimited Range*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms PENUGONDA NAGASAI ANANDA KRISHNA HANUMA bearing USN 1SU21EC022 has completed his/her minor project on “*Remote Controlled Robotic Arm*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PIYUSH P** bearing **USN 1SU21EC023** has completed his/her minor project on “*Automation Of Ration Products Distribution System*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms POORNAPRAJNA P bearing USN 1SU21EC024 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Wireless Load Controller By GSM* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RANJITHA B N bearing USN 1SU21EC025 has completed his/her minor project on ***“GSM Unmanned Arial Photography Using Remote Flying Robot”*** in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RANJU K W bearing USN 1SU21EC026 has completed his/her minor project on *“GSM Digital Security Systems for Printer”* in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **REVANTH N** bearing **USN 1SU21EC027** has completed his/her minor project on ***“Sensor Based Motion Control Of Mobile Car Robot”*** in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SAKETH S bearing USN 1SU21EC028 has completed his/her minor project on “*Voice Operated Intelligent Fire Extinguisher Vehicle*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SREYAS SUNIL bearing USN 1SU21EC029 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Nav Multi Processor System* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VINAYALAL H bearing USN 1SU21EC030 has completed his/her minor project on “*Digital Stopwatch*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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